

THE IMPACT OF PERSONALITY TRAITS ON WORK OUTCOMES OF OFFICERS AT ADMINISTRATIVE UNITS OF THE HANOI PEOPLE'S COMMITTEE IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

The study aims to analyse the impact of personality traits on work outcomes of officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee in Vietnam. A questionnaire survey was conducted to collect data from 455 officers at the Administrative units. Collected data were analysed by using structural equation model (SEM) to evaluate the impact of personality traits on work outcomes including job satisfaction, organisational commitment and intention to stay. The results revealed that a positive relationship between the Big Five personality traits with organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay. Furthermore, job satisfaction and organisational commitment are positively correlated with intention to stay in an organisation of officers at Hanoi People's Committee. The result of the study suggested some significant implications for the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee to increase organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and upgrade intention to stay of officers in the coming time.

Keywords: Big Five Personality Traits, Organisational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Intention to Stay, Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the backbone of all activities in the organisation, and it directly affects the existence, development, and competition of the organisation. If an organisation wants to achieve good performance, it needs good employee performance. Employee performance is the total value expected by the organisation of the personal behavioural characteristics of employees performing a job at a given time to contribute to organisational effectiveness (Borman et al., 2003).

In the public sector, officers make significant contributions to the development and success of a country and constitute the human resources of society. Officers have a specific character because of their close association with the operation of the state apparatus and their development based on socio-economic background (Hai, 2013). The president Ho Chi Minh confirmed the role of officers in the revolution in the sentence "officers are the root of everything" (Minh, 2002).

The studies on organisational behaviour focus on analysing personality traits. They concluded that personality traits have a direct impact on an employee's thoughts, behaviour, and social relationships (Allameh et al., 2012; Delima, 2020). Hence, personality traits are an important tool for evaluating employee performance (Saville and Holdsworth, 1999).

The studies focused on the impact of personality traits on job performance of employees (Pham, 2013; Tran, 2019). However, those studies only analysed the job performance aspect of work outcomes.

In addition, they don't investigate the public sector. In particular, there are no empirical investigation study at Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee. Thus, to fill in the research gap, the article aims to analyse impact on personality traits on work outcomes (organisational commitment, job satisfaction, intention to stay) of officers at Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee. Based on the analysis results, the study suggests policy implications to improve work outcomes of officers working at Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee in the future.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Literature review

2.1.1. Personality traits

Bradberry (2007) defined personality as the trait of each person, creating a distinction between people from a psychological perspective and making a person unique with different psychological characteristics. Personality traits are the totality of a process that includes feelings, thoughts, and behaviours of a person (Carpenter and Moore, 2009).

Many studies explored human personality. Klages (1926) showed the words nature uses to describe the personality of each person. Allport and Odbert (1936) found 18,000 words in the English dictionary to describe the personality of each person. Cattell (1946) made an effort to arrange and shorten the above words to give 12 base characteristics that show each person's personality. Up to 1981, Goldberg concluded that each person's personality is composed of five different characteristics, and he named it the "Big Five" personality traits model. This name does not denote the vastness of the five factors. Goldberg wants to describe per factor that can use to assess most of the personality of an individual. The studies of Hogan (1986), Buss (1989) have given different names for each personality, but the Big Five model is perfectly suitable to describe the trait that exists inside each person (Digman, 1990; Judge et al., 2002).

The OCEAN model of Costa and McCrae (1992) is one of the most recognised and frequently used models in research on personality traits. The studies of Kheng et al. (2013), Tran (2015) changed neuroticism to emotional stability to be appropriate in the research process. In this study, the Big Five personality traits model used include:

Openness to experience is related to the characteristics of love of adventure, strong personality, mind, imagination, many interests, creative intelligence, desire to learn about the world around, and love to learn or enjoy new experiences. People who are open to experimenting tend to be open-hearted, willing to challenge new things, liberal, and not subject to rules and hard to predict.

Conscientiousness is associated with the characteristics of thoughtfulness, hard work, keeping firmly, a sense of responsibility in everything, and in cases considered workaholics. A conscientious person is diligent, dedicated in all work, lives and works in compliance with the rules, acts in everything with careful consideration and wins the trust of people around. A conscientious person is diligent, hardworking in all things, lives, and works following the rules.

They act in everything with careful consideration and win the trust of people around.

Extroversion is related to the characteristics of like to exchange relations or participate in community activities, enthusiastic, friendly, full of positive energy, and leading an active life. Extroverts like to work in groups, are confident, active at work, talkative, and easily communicate with people around them.

Agreeableness is related to the traits of sociability, modest, swallowing the bitter pill, forgive, gentleness in all relationships, cheerfulness, and not being easily angered. Agreeableness people often put their trust in others. They are willing to cooperate, listen to ideas, help, share difficulties, and receive love from those around them.

Emotional stability is related to positive traits in controlling emotions, being able to stay balanced, calm, and cope well in any situation. People with emotional stability are calm, do not give up easily, and are not easily swayed by emotions. They work hard to find solutions to problems that arise, don't take long to recover from events, and they are comfortable in life's relationships (Emotional stability is the opposite of neuroticism).

2.1.2. Work outcomes

Work outcomes refers to as the results or impact of activities of an individual over a given period. Evaluating employees' performance is necessary to achieve the goals set by the organisation for them. If the employee's performance is better, it will create positive results, mainly including employee satisfaction, commitment in the workplace, etc (Usha and Rohini, 2018). In this study, work outcomes related to personality traits are analysed includes organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay in an organisation.

2.1.2.1. Organisational commitment

Organisational commitment is a multi-directional structure, and it is considered based on employees' feelings towards the organisation. The concept of organisational commitment of Porter et al. (1974) is a strong belief in and acceptance of the goals and values of the organisation, a willingness to represent the organisation, and a desire to maintain membership of the organisation. Mowday et al. (1979) indicated that organisational commitment is the consistency between employees with the goals, values of the organisation, and active participation in the organisation. Up to 2001, Meyer and Herscovitch defined organisational commitment is the belief in the organisation, agreement with the goals and common values of the organisation, the effort to contribute to the best of their ability for the organisation, and desire to stay with the organisation for a long time.

Meyer and Allen (1991) demonstrated that organisational commitment is composed of three distinct components including (i) affective commitment is the psychological connection between employees and the organisation; (ii) continuance commitment is employees will lose in costs if they leave the organisation; (iii) normative commitment is employees always feel a sense of responsibility towards the organisation. The study of Meyer and Allen focused on positive psychological attitudes between employees and the organisation. In addition, Meyer and Allen (1997) showed that if employees have a high level of organisational commitment,

they will appear to believe in the values of an organisation, focus on their work, and make a positive contribution to the organisation. The scale of Meyer and Allen is commonly used in research on organisational commitment (Benkhoff, 1997; Tran, 2006).

2.1.2.2. Job satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction has received a lot of attention in researches on organisational behaviour. However, the studies approach from different perspectives, so the concept of job satisfaction is not uniform. Job satisfaction is how employees rate their work based on the aspects of their work that they think are important (Sempane et al., 2002) or an employee's level of emotional response to different angles of the job (Luddy, 2005). The study of Robbins (2003) argued that job satisfaction is a general attitude of employees towards their work, indicating positive and negative emotional states of employees towards work (Armstrong, 2006), or how employees perceive their current job (Kitchel et al., 2012).

Spector (1997) concluded that job satisfaction approaches and measures in two directions, including different aspects and overall job satisfaction. Tran (2005) agrees with Spector (1997). She pointed out that different aspects of job satisfaction are attitudes and perceptions of employees about the nature of work, training and promotion, co-workers, income, leadership, welfare, and working conditions. In contrast, overall job satisfaction is the feeling that employees feel comfortable, happy, and satisfied if they achieve the needs and desires set out in the job. Measuring by different aspects will give the best results if assessing employee satisfaction because it considers each angle that makes employees feel satisfied and those that do not bring pleasure to employees. However, the studies confirmed the grave role of overall satisfaction in measuring employee job satisfaction (Slatten, 2008). Hence, two approaches are suitable for measuring employee job satisfaction.

2.1.2.3. Intention to stay

The intention is the consciousness of each human being indicated by the fact that they are always ready to perform a given behaviour and will decide based on previous behaviours (Ajzen, 1991). Price and Mueller (1981) defined intention to stay in an organisation as an employee's commitment to the organisation, which helps the organisation reduce the costs incurred related to employees and motivates employees to do their best to build a growing organisation. Tett & Meyer (1993) indicated that intention to stay in an organisation is the level of commitment between employees and the organisation, and it expresses through their willingness to remain at the organisation. Intention to stay in the organisation reflects the employee's satisfaction and acceptance of what the organisation offer for them, and they perceive the possibility of future self-development (Van Breukelen et al., 2004). Or the intention to stay in the organisation is the employee's integration and willingness to stay with the organisation for a long time (Johanim et al., 2012). The studies confirmed the importance of the intention to stay in the organisation because if the employees intend to leave, they will cause negative consequences in human resource management at the organisation (Dalessio et al., 1986; Shaw et al., 2005). In addition, intention to stay in the organisation is the opposite of intention to leave (Kim et al., 1996), so, based on studies on intention to leave, it is possible to infer studies on intention to

stay in the organisation. The intention is the premise for all actual behaviour, so the behaviour of staying in or leaving the organisation will be influenced by the intention to remain in the organisation or the intention to leave. Hence, intention to stay or intention to leave is the best predictor of actual actions of employees.

2.2. Hypothesis development

2.2.1. The relationship between personality traits and organisational commitment

The elements of personality traits are antecedents and predictors of employees' commitment to the organisation (Cui, 2010). In addition, the studies of Judge et al. (2002), Kuldeep and Bakhshi (2010), Hawass (2012) found a positive relationship between the elements of personality traits and organisational commitment of employees. Erdheim et al. (2006) showed that extroverts will have higher affective commitment compared to continuance and normative commitment. At the same time, conscientiousness and agreeableness have related to the three components of organisational commitment. Besides, neuroticism has an inverse relationship with organisational commitment. On the other hand, openness to experience and affective commitment is not statistically significant. The research results of Kuldeep & Bakhshi (2010) are completely consistent with the study of Erdheim et al. (2006). Sadeghi & Yazdanbakhsh (2014) concluded that Big Five personality traits have a positive impact on three components of organisational commitment. They emphasized neuroticism has the heaviest impact on organisational commitment but inverse. Furthermore, agreeableness has a direct impact on three components of organisational commitment (Naquin and Holton, 2002). Therefore, the first hypothesis group proposed in the study is:

H1.1: Openness to experience has a positive impact on organisational commitment

H1.2: Conscientiousness has a positive impact on organisational commitment

H1.3: Extroversion has a positive impact on organisational commitment

H1.4: Agreeableness has a positive impact on organisational commitment

H1.5: Emotional stability has a positive impact on organisational commitment

2.2.2. The relationship between personality traits and job satisfaction

The studies demonstrated that the Big Five personality traits model affects job satisfaction (Barrick and Mount, 1991; Bergh and Theron, 2003; Thoresen et al., 2004). Zhai et al. (2013) indicated that Big Five personality traits and job satisfaction are big correlated with different levels. In which extroversion has the heaviest positive correlation, the second is the openness to experience, the third is neuroticism with the inverse effect, the fourth is agreeableness, and the last is conscientiousness with the lowest correlation. Yildirim et al. (2016) concluded that extroversion and openness to experience have a heaviest impact on job satisfaction of employees. In contrast, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and sociability has no impact on the job satisfaction of employees. Unlike Yildirim et al. (2016), the study of Khizar et al. (2016) indicated that Big Five personality traits have a significant impact on job satisfaction of employees. With neuroticism has a heaviest inverse impact on job satisfaction. Extroversion,

agreeableness, and conscientiousness have a positive impact on job satisfaction. And openness to experience has no impact on job satisfaction of them. Hence, the second hypothesis group proposed in the study is:

- H2.1: Openness to experience has a positive impact on job satisfaction
- H2.2: Conscientiousness has a positive impact on job satisfaction
- H2.3: Extroversion has a positive impact on job satisfaction
- H2.4: Agreeableness has a positive impact on job satisfaction
- H2.5: Emotional stability has a positive impact on job satisfaction

2.2.3. The relationship between personality traits and intention to stay in an organisation

The studies demonstrated the relationship between Big Five personality traits with turnover intention of employees (Ashton et al., 2000; Chiu et al., 2005) and they obtained the different results. Barrick and Mount (1991) concluded that there is no relationship between conscientiousness and employee satisfaction. Up to 1996, Barrick and Mount pointed out that conscientiousness has an inverse relationship with turnover intention of employees. The study of Salgado (2002) found an inverse correlation of Big Five personality traits (extroversion, agreeableness, emotional stability, openness to experience, conscientiousness) with turnover intention. Zimmerman (2008) argued that turnover intention is not affected by extroversion and emotional stability. But it is negatively affected by agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience. Agreeableness has an inverse impact on turnover intention, and extroversion has a positive effect on the intention to quit (Day et al., 1998). In addition, emotional stability harms turnover intention (Sawyer et al., 2008). In Vietnam, the study of Le et al. (2015) indicated that conscientiousness and emotional stability have an inverse impact on turnover intention, or employees with these two characteristics will have less intention to quit. The third hypothesis group proposed in the study is:

- H3.1: Openness to experience has a positive on intention to stay in an organisation
- H3.2: Conscientiousness has a positive on intention to stay in an organisation
- H3.3: Extroversion has a positive on intention to stay in an organisation
- H3.4: Agreeableness has a positive on intention to stay in an organisation
- H3.5: Emotional stability has a positive on intention to stay in an organisation

2.2.4. The relationship between organisational commitment, job satisfaction and intention to stay in an organisation

Many studies showed that organisational commitment and job satisfaction have a strong inverse impact on the turnover intention of employees (Porter et al., 1976; Tett and Meyer, 1993). The study framework of Martin and Roodt (2008) confirmed the relationship between organisational commitment and job satisfaction with turnover intention. The results pointed out that they have an inverse correlation with intention to quit. In which, job satisfaction has a more

correlation than organisational commitment with intention to quit. Aydogdu and Asikgil (2011) affirmed that the intention to quit is strongly (negatively) influenced by two factors of organisational commitment and job satisfaction. In Vietnam, Vu and Nguyen (2018) found a direct inverse relationship between organisational commitment and job satisfaction with the turnover intention of employees. The study of Nguyen and Ho (2020) discovered that organisational commitment and job satisfaction have a positive impact on intention to stay in an organisation of employees. The fourth and fifth hypothesis proposed in the study is:

H4: Organisational commitment has a positive impact on intention to stay in an organisation.

H5: Job satisfaction has a positive impact on intention to stay in an organisation.

From the hypotheses, the authors propose the study framework by following:

Figure 1: Research Model

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. Measures of study

Preliminary scale is built based on the factors in the study framework and inherited from domestic and foreign studies. In which, the scale of the Big Five personality traits model come into of Tran (2015) include twenty observed variables. The scale of organisational commitment includes six observed variables of Meyer and Allen (1993). The scale of job satisfaction inherited of Tran (2005) includes five observed variables. The scale of intention to stay includes four observed variables of Huynh (2012).

To be relevant to the field of study, the authors discussed with fourteen department-level managers with long-term experience working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee to carefully review the content related to factors, add or remove inappropriate observed variables.

In addition, in-depth interviews were conducted with five experts on human resource management to understand the relationships between factors, adjust the study framework and solve problems arising during the discussion. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the authors conducted group discussions and in-depth interviews using Microsoft Team.

The quantitative research results showed that discussion managers and experts agree with factors in the proposed study framework. For the Big Five personality traits model, 3/5 experts and 10/14 discussion managers think that it is necessary to need to add one observed variable to each personality trait so that the content of each personality shows more clearly and meet the requirements of research in the public sector. For the intention to stay in an organisation, experts and discussion managers said that the item of the observed variables in the original scale is not suitable for examination in the public sector, and they need to change. Based on the above comments, the authors synthesised and built four observed variables of intention to stay in an organisation. For the organisational commitment and job satisfaction, experts and discussion managers agree with the question in the original scale. In addition, the authors adjusted words to be consistent for the public sector and the education level of survey participants. The survey items for all the variables used in the study are presented in table 1.

3.2. Sample and Data collection

Hair et al. (2014) stated that the minimum sample size to use exploratory factor analysis is 50 observations, preferably 100 or more observations. The ratio of observations on an analytic variable of 5:1 or 10:1 will provide the minimum sample size of the study to ensure reliability. In this study, the authors use the 10:1 rule. This study has 40 observed variables, so the number of samples needed is $40 \times 10 = 400$. Besides, to avoid the low probability of a vote recovery, the authors will take the sample size of 490 observations.

The study used a convenient sampling method for officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee. The survey period is from May 1st to July 31st, 2021. The survey forms were sent directly by email to officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee.

The study investigated 7 Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee (include Hanoi Tax Department, Ha Noi Customs Department, Hanoi Statistics Department, Hanoi Market Surveillance Department, Hanoi Social Security Office, Hanoi State Treasury, and The State Bank in Hanoi Branch). The authors divided the survey questionnaires equally among the research sites as $490/7 \text{ units} = 70 \text{ bollocks/unit}$. The authors divided equally among 7 units to show an objective and fair assessment among them at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee. After the cleaning the data, the study collected 455 valid answer sheets with a return rate of 92.86%. Male respondents constituted 67.2% of the sample. 91.4% of respondents were middleaged (more than 35 years old), 92.5% of respondents with the education level is mainly university and post-graduate, and 91.7% of respondents got married.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that the latent variable “Extroversion” has the lowest Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.778, while the latent variable “Conscientiousness” has the highest of 0.852. Compared with standard 0.6, all observed items of the scale are internally consistent. The corrected item-total correlation coefficient is higher than 0.3. Cronbach’s alpha if items deleted of all 40 observed items is lower than Cronbach’s Alpha value, which indicates that no items are removed (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). All scales achieve two reliability and discriminant validity. Hence, the scale is good and meets the reliable requirement for exploratory factor analysis.

The study used the Principal Axis Factoring extraction method along with Promax rotation. The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is conducted with 40 observed items from eight factors include the Big Five personality traits, job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and intention to stay. The EFA obtained results with the coefficient KMO = 0.812; Bartlett Test is statistically significant with Sig. = 0.000 (< 0.05), and eight factors were extracted with Eigenvalue = 1.422; Sums of Squared Loadings = 80.121% (higher than 50%). And the eight factors can explain about 80.121% of the variance of all the variables from the total variance explained (Hair et al., 1998). Table 1 summarised the results of Cronbach’s alpha and exploratory factor analysis of the overall scale.

Table 1: Survey items and reliability for measures in the study

Abbr.	Items	Source	Cronbach’s Alpha	Item loadings
Openness to experience				
O1	You have new ideas if you run into problems.	Tran (2015)	0.823	0.899
O2	You enjoy new ideas and initiatives.			0.895
O3	You easily adapt to new ideas.			0.890
O4	You like variety and complexity in your work.			0.883
O5	You are ready to accept any change of position of the agency.	Self-developed		0.881
Conscientiousness				
C1	You can start working right away.	Tran (2015)	0.852	0.897
C2	You work with a high sense of responsibility and iron discipline.			0.894
C3	You work in accordance with the work process.			0.893
C4	You pay attention to the smallest details.			0.888
C5	You are hardworking and zeal to your work.	Self-developed		0.880
Extroversion				
E1	You actively participate in collective activities at the agency.	Tran (2015)	0.778	0.889
E2	You often talk and discuss with colleagues about work.			0.885
E3	You can communicate with many different types of people at the agency.			0.879
E4	You are confident to present and contribute ideas at work.			0.975
E5	You are ready and full of energy to do the job.	Self-		0.870

		developed		
Agreeableness				
A1	You have the same opinion as your colleagues.	Tran (2015)	0.803	0.882
A2	You and your colleagues solve all problems at work.			0.877
A3	You regularly participate in community activities.			0.874
A4	You act to make people feel comfortable.			0.870
A5	You have belief, sympathy, and a willingness to forgive people.	Self-developed		0.869
Emotional stability				
ES1	You always keep calm to solve problems at work.	Tran (2015)	0.811	0.878
ES2	You always have a comfortable psychology state at work.			0.869
ES3	You always control your emotions to solve delicate problems at work.			0.865
ES4	You always control yourself well against the pressures of work.			0.860
ES5	You always maintain firm political stuff at work.	Self-developed		0.858
Organisational commitment				
OC1	You feel happy to spend the rest of your career at the agency.	Meyer, Allen and Smith (1993)	0.799	0.868
OC2	You realise that all the problems of the agency are also your problems.			0.864
OC3	You feel that you belong to the agency.			0.855
OC4	You feel a strong emotional bond with the agency.			0.852
OC5	You feel you are part of an agency.			0.850
OC6	You realise that the agency has an important meaning to you.			0.844
Job satisfaction				
JS1	You are happy to choose the agency as the place to work.	Tran (2005)	0.808	0.866
JS2	You would choose the agency if you had the chance to choose again.			0.859
JS3	You find the office to be the best place to work.			0.853
JS4	You consider your work as a second home.			0.848
JS5	Generally speaking, you are satisfied to work at the agency.			0.840
Intention to stay				
ITS1	You have never intended to find another job.	Self-developed	0.840	0.863
ITS2	You have never thought about leaving the organisation.			0.851
ITS3	You feel that your career has a good opportunity to develop at the office.			0.843
ITS4	You will only leave the agency if you reach retirement age.			0.838

The results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) indicated that the model has 1,432 degrees of freedom, the test value CMIN = 432.674 with the probability value = 0.000; the CMIN/df index = 2.532 is lower than 3.0 (Carmines and McIver, 1981) and the goodness-of-fit index (GFI) = 0.906, the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) = 0.910, the comparative fit index (CFI) = 0.915 are higher than 0.9 (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007), the root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) = 0.030 is lower than 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). So, the research model is consistent with the research data.

Figure 2: The results of the confirmatory factor analysis of the overall model scale

The results of CFA of the overall model scale show that the weights of the observed variables are all standard (≥ 0.5). Hence, the scales reach the convergent validity (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). In addition, there is no correlation between the measurement errors, so the observed variables achieve unidimensionality. The correlation coefficient of each research concept is significantly different from 1, so the components reach discriminant values. The analysis results also show that the scales meet the requirements of reliability (Steenkamp and Van Trijp, 1991).

Furthermore, the authors test the scale's reliability. The reliability test results indicated that the composite reliability and the total variance extracted value are higher than 0.5. Besides, the overall reliability of greater than 0.6. Hence, the analytical results showed that all the research model concepts meet the requirement of high reliability. Therefore, the scale is suitable for the analysis of the structural equation modeling (Hair et al., 2014; Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Based on the outcomes of the confirmatory factor analysis of the overall model scale, the results of the structural equation modeling are consistent with the research data. That is shown by the CMIN/df index = $2.567 < 3$ (Carmines and McIver, 1981) and the GFI = 0.904, TLI = 0.907,

CFI = 0.912 are higher than 0.9 (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007); RMSEA = 0.035 is lower than 0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999).

At the same time, based on the analysis results, the probability value of the impact relationships between the factors is lower than 0.05. Hence, the relationship between Big Five personality traits, job satisfaction, organisational commitment and intention to stay is statistically significant in the structural equation modeling (SEM). Table 2 summarised the model results.

Table 2: SEM the results test the relationship between the concepts in the research model

Variables	Organisational commitment			Job satisfaction			Intention to stay		
	Hypothesis	Hypothesized direction	Path coefficient	Hypothesis	Hypothesized direction	Path coefficient	Hypothesis	Hypothesized direction	Path coefficient
O	H1.1	+	0.213*	H2.1	+	0.211**	H3.1	+	0.216*
C	H1.2	+	0.354**	H2.2	+	0.362**	H3.2	+	0.371**
E	H1.3	+	0.257**	H2.3	+	0.223*	H3.3	+	0.241**
A	H1.4	+	0.321*	H2.4	+	0.333**	H3.4	+	0.313*
ES	H1.5	+	0.205*	H2.5	+	0.121*	H3.5	+	0.212**
OC	-	-	-	-	-	-	H4	+	0.389*
JS	-	-	-	-	-	-	H5	+	0.391*
ITS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

* indicate that the path coefficient are significant at 0.1; ** indicate that the path coefficient are significant at 0.05

The results in table 2 pointed out that the Big Five personality traits have a positive impact on organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay in an organisation. In which, conscientiousness has the strongest impact on organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay with 95% confidence and the standardised estimate of 0.354, 0.362, 0.371. Emotional stability has a weakest impact on organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay in an organisation with a standardised estimate of 0.205, 0.121, 0.212. The results are similar to the studies of Hawass (2012), Khizar et al. (2016), Chiu et al., (2005). Hence, hypothesis group H1, H2, H3 are accepted.

The results of structural equation modeling confirmed that organisational commitment and job satisfaction have a positive impact on intention to stay of officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People’s Committee. The result is similar to the study of Nguyen and Ho (2020). So, hypothesis H4, H5 are accepted.

Thus, the Big Five personality traits have direct impact on organisational commitment, job satisfaction and intention to stay of officers. That is the highlight of the study and making a difference from the studies of Pham (2013), Tran (2019). Because the previous studies did not measure organisational commitment job satisfaction, and job performance of officers in the public sector based on personality traits. Hence, the study could create a paradigm for future studies on confirming the relationship between personality traits with organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay in the public sector.

5. POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The findings from the present study add to the body of theoretical about the study of the Administrative units by examining the personality traits are related to work outcomes. The study also reported that conscientiousness is the heaviest predictor of organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay, followed by agreeableness, extroversion, openness to experience and emotional stability, respectively. Hence, based on the obtained results, the study provides policy implications to help the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee improve organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and increase intention to stay of officers following:

First, to improve the conscientiousness and agreeableness of officers, administrators need to manage people effectively. Administrators need to make officers understand the vision, common goals, and future direction of the agency. At the same time, the agency must make employees understand the importance and their contribution to the organisation or the value of the work they are doing.

Second, to improve the extroversion of officers, administrators should organise training courses to develop professional qualifications, foreign languages, soft skills such as public speaking, teamwork skills, organising cultural activities, etc. These activities will help officers build and develop openness and friendliness towards others, contribute to developing officers' extroversion.

Third, to improve the openness to experience, the agency needs to develop new skills training policies for officers. Besides, the agency should build reward policies for officers with new ideas and creativity at work. Hence, encourage and improve the openness of employees to experience.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, the impact of personality traits on work outcomes (organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay) analysis through the data set obtained by the direct survey method of officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee. Confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation modeling analyses were performed to confirm the relationship between the constructs in the study framework. The analysis results show that a direct impact of personality traits on organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and intention to stay in an organisation. On the other hand, job satisfaction and organisational commitment have a direct impact on intention to stay of officers working at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

There are still some limitations of the study, including (i) the small limited sample size. The study was conducted only at the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee; (ii) the study tested the hypothesis by collecting data from officers the Administrative units of the Hanoi People's Committee with a convenient sampling method.

Therefore, some implications for future research could include: (i) increase the sample size or extend the scope; (ii) future studies should consider the impact of personality traits on work outcomes using the probability sampling method to increase the generalizability of the study.

References

- 1) Ajen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), pp. 179-211.
- 2) Allameh, S. M., Ghafari, M. and Davoodi, S. M. R. (2012). Studying Impact of Personality Traits on Job Performance: The Case of University of Isfahan's Personnel. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(6), pp. 6293-6399.
- 3) Allport, G. W. and Odbert, H. S. (1936). Trait-names: A psycho-lexical study. *Psychological Monographs*, 47(1), pp. i-171.
- 4) Anderson, J. C. and Gerbing, D. W. (1988). Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 3(2), pp. 411-423.
- 5) Armstrong, M. (2006). *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice (10th Edition)*. London: Kogan Page Publishing.
- 6) Ashton, M. C., Lee, K. and Son, C. (2000). Honesty as the sixth factor of personality: correlations with Machiavellianism, Primary Psychopathy, and Social Adroitness. *European Journal of Personality*, 14(4), pp. 359-368.
- 7) Aydogdu, S. and Asikgil, B. (2011). An Empirical Study of the Relationship among Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 1(3), pp. 43-53.
- 8) Barrick, M. R. and Mount, M. K. (1991). The Big Five personality dimensions and job performance: A meta-analysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 44(1), pp. 1-26.
- 9) Barrick, M. R. and Mount, M. K. (1996). Effects of impression management and self-deception on the predictive validity of personality constructs. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(3), pp. 261-272.
- 10) Benkhoff, B. (1997). Ignoring commitment is costly: New approaches establish the missing link between commitment and performance. *Human Relations*, 50(6), pp. 701-726.
- 11) Bergh, Z. C. and Theron, A. L. (2003). *Psychology in the work context (2nd ed)*. Cape Town: Oxford University Press Southern Africa.
- 12) Borman, G., Hewes, G., Overman, L. and Brown, S. (2003). Comprehensive school reform and achievement: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 72(3), pp. 125-230.
- 13) Bradberry, T. (2007). *The personality code: Unlock the secret to understanding your boss, your colleagues, your friends - and yourself*. London: Penguin.
- 14) Buss, A. H. (1989). Personality as traits. *American Psychologist*, 44(11), pp. 1378-1388.
- 15) Carmines, E. G. and McIver, J. P. (1981). Analysing Models with Unobserved Variables: Analysis of Covariance Structures. In Bohrnstedt, G.W. and Borgatta, E.F. (Eds.), *Social Measurement: Current Issues*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
- 16) Carpenter, J. M. and Moore, M. (2009). Utilitarian and hedonic shopping value in the US discount sector. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 16(1), pp. 68-74.
- 17) Cattell, R. B. (1946). *Description and measurement of personality*, World Book Company.

- 18) Chiu, C., Chien, C., Lin, C. and Hsiao, C. Y. (2005). Understanding hospital employee job stress and turnover intentions in a practical setting: the moderating role of locus of control. *The Journal of Management Development*, 24(10), pp. 837-845.
- 19) Costa, P.T. and McCrae, R. R. (1992). The five-factor model of personality and its relevance to personality disorders. *Journal of Personality Disorders*, 6(4), pp. 343-359.
- 20) Cui, C. (2010). *The Relationship among Personality Traits, Job Design Characteristics and Organizational Commitment: An Empirical Study of Organizations in China*. Master Thesis, The University of Waikato, Waikato.
- 21) Dalessio, A., Silverman, W. and Schuck, J. (1986). Paths to turnover: a re-analysis and review of existing data on the Mobley, Horner, and Hollingsworth's turnover model. *Human Relations*, 39(3), pp. 245-264.
- 22) Day, D. V., Bedein, A. G. and Conte, J. M. (1998). Personality as predictor of work-related outcomes: test of a mediated latent structural model. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 28, pp. 2068-2088.
- 23) Delima, V. J. (2020). Impact of Personality Traits on Employees' Job Performance in Batticaloa Teaching Hospital. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 2(12), pp. 86-97.
- 24) Digman, J. M. (1990). Personality structure: Emergence of the five-factor model. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 41(1), pp. 417-440.
- 25) Erdheim, J., Wang, M. and Zickar, M. J. (2006). Linking the Big Five personality constructs to organizational commitment. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 41(5), pp. 959-970.
- 26) Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), pp. 39-50.
- 27) Goldberg, L. R. (1981). Language and individual differences: The search for universals in personality lexicons. *Review of personality and social psychology*, 2(1), pp. 141-165.
- 28) Hai, T. N. (2013). *Completing the law on civil servants and public servants to meet the requirements of State administrative reform*. Hanoi, Vietnam: Judicial Publishing House.
- 29) Hair, J. F. J., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L. and Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM): An Emerging Tool for Business Research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), pp. 106-121.
- 30) Hair, J. F. J., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L. and Black, W. C. (1998). *Multivariate Data Analysis (5th edn)*. Prentice Hall College Div, Upper Saddle River.
- 31) Hawass, H. H. (2012). Committed Salesforce: An Investigation into Personality Traits. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(6), pp. 147-160.
- 32) Hogan, R. (1986). Hogan Personality Inventory. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counseling and Development*, 21(3), pp. 139-140.
- 33) Hu, L. and Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 6(1), pp. 1-55.
- 34) Huynh, H. T. (2012). *Factors Influencing Organizational Commitment and Intention to Stay of Core Employees in Small - Medium Sized Companies in Ho Chi Minh City*. Master Thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.
- 35) Johanim, J., Yean, T. F., Adnan, Z., Yahya, K., Yahya, D. and Nassruddin, M. (2012). Promoting Employee Intention to Stay: Do Human Resource Management Practices Matter?. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 6(2), pp. 396-416.

- 36) Judge, T. A., Heller, D. and Mount, M. K. (2002). Five-Factor Model of Personality and Job Satisfaction: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(3), pp. 530-541.
- 37) Kheng, Y. K., June, S. and Mahmood, R. (2013). The Determinants of Innovative Work Behavior in the Knowledge Intensive Business Services Sector in Malaysia. *Asian Social Science*, 9(15), pp. 47-59.
- 38) Khizar, U., Orcullo, D. J. C. and Mustafa, J. (2016). Relationship between Personality Traits and Job Satisfaction of Police Officers in Punjab, Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(7), pp. 109-113.
- 39) Kim, S., Price, J. L., Mueller, C. W. and Watson, T. W. (1996). The determinants of career intent among physicians at a U.S. Air Force hospital. *Human Relations*, 49(7), pp. 947-976.
- 40) Kitchel, T., Smith, A., Henry, A., Robinson, S., Lawver, R., Park, T. and Schell, A. (2012). Teacher Job Satisfaction and Burnout Viewed through Social Comparisons. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 53(1), pp. 31-44.
- 41) Klages, L. (1926). *The science of character*. UK: Allen & Unwin.
- 42) Kuldeep, K. and Bakhshi, A. (2010). The Five-Factor Model of Personality and Organizational Commitment: Is There Any Relationship. *Humanity and Social Sciences Journal*, 5(1), pp. 25-34.
- 43) Le, L. P., Nguyen, Y. H. T. and Banh, U. U. T. (2015). Studying the impact of personality factors on the effectiveness of call center service and the intention to quit of operators. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science – Economics and Business Administration*, 10(3), pp. 63-74.
- 44) Luddy, N. (2005). *Job satisfaction amongst employees at a public health institution in the Western Cape*. University of Western Cape, South Africa.
- 45) Martin, A. and Roodt, G. (2008). Perceptions of organisational commitment, job satisfaction and turnover intentions in a post merger tertiary institution. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 34(1), pp. 23-31.
- 46) Meyer, J. P. and Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), pp. 61-89.
- 47) Meyer, J. P. and Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research, and application*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- 48) Meyer, J. P. and Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the Workplace: Toward a General Model. *Human Resource Management Review*, 11(3), pp. 299-326.
- 49) Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J. and Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78(4), pp. 538-551.
- 50) Minh, H.C. (2002). *Ho Chi Minh full volume*. Hanoi, Vietnam: National Political Publishing House.
- 51) Mowday, R. T., Steers, R. M. and Porter, L. W. (1979). The Measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 14(2), pp. 224-247.
- 52) Naquin, S. S. and Holton, E. F. III. (2002). The effects of personality, affectivity, and work commitment on motivation to improve work through learning. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 13(4), pp. 357-376.
- 53) Nguyen, T. T. and Ho, D. T. (2020). Factor impact the job satisfaction, the commitment to the organisation and the intention to stay of staff working in Ho Chi Minh City's information industry sector. *Industry and Trade Magazine*, 1, pp. 1-7.
- 54) Nunnally, J. C. and Bernstein, I. H. (1994). The Assessment of Reliability. *Psychometric Theory*, 3, pp. 248-292.

- 55) Pham, P. T. K. (2013). *Measuring Personality Factors Affecting Work Outcomes of Employees in Bank*. Master Thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.
- 56) Porter, L. W., Crampon, W. J. and Smith, F. J. (1976). Organizational commitment and managerial turnover: A longitudinal study. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 15(1), pp. 87-98.
- 57) Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T. and Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), pp. 603-609.
- 58) Price, J. L. and Mueller, C. W. (1981). A causal model of turnover for nurses. *Academy of Management Journal*, 24(3), pp. 543-565.
- 59) Robbins, S. P (2003). *Organizational behaviour concepts, controversies, application (8th ed)*. New Jersey, USA: Prentice-hall International.
- 60) Sadeghi, P. and Yazdanbakhsh, K. (2014). The Relationship between the Big Five Personality Factors and the Willingness and Organizational Commitment of Teachers. *Applied mathematics in Engineering, Management and Technology*, 2(5), pp. 28-36.
- 61) Salgado, J. F. (2002). The Big Five Personality Dimensions and Counterproductive Behaviors. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 10(1-2), pp. 117-125.
- 62) Saville and Holdsworth Ltd. (1999). *Occupational Personality Questionnaires (OPQ 32) manual*. Surrey: Saville & Holdsworth.
- 63) Sawyerr, O. O., Srinivas, S. and Wang, S. (2009). Call center employee personality factors and service performance. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 23(5), pp. 301-317.
- 64) Sempane, M., Rieger, H. and Roodt, G. (2002). Job Satisfaction in Relation to Organizational Culture. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 28(2), pp. 23-30.
- 65) Shaw, J. D., Gupta, N. and Delery, J. E. (2005). Alternative conceptualizations of the relationship between voluntary turnover and organizational performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(1), pp. 50-68.
- 66) Slatten, T. (2008). Antecedents and effects of emotional satisfaction on employee-perceived service quality. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 18(4), pp. 370-386.
- 67) Spector, P. E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- 68) Steenkamp, J. B. E. and Van Trijp, H. (1991). The Use of LISREL in Validating Marketing Constructs. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 8, pp. 283-299.
- 69) Tabachnick, B. G. and Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using Multivariate Statistics (5th ed.)*. Pearson, Boston.
- 70) Tett, R. P. and Meyer, J. P. (1993). Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Turnover Intention, and Turnover: Path Analyses Based on Meta-Analytic Findings. *Personnel Psychology*, 46(2), pp. 259-293.
- 71) Thoresen, C. J., Bradley, J. C., Bliese, P. D. and Thoresen, J. D. (2004). The Big Five Personality Traits and Individual Job Performance Growth Trajectories in Maintenance and Transitional Job Stages. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), pp. 835-853.
- 72) Tran, C. N. (2019). *The relationship between personality traits, job satisfaction and job outcomes of employees in Ho Chi Minh City*. Master Thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.
- 73) Tran, D. K. (2005). Measuring job satisfaction in Vietnam. *Journal of Economics Development*, 8(12), pp. 85-91.

- 74) Tran, D. K. (2006). The scale of sense of organisational commitment. *Journal of Economics Development*, 184, pp. 50-52.
- 75) Tran, T. A. D. (2015). *Personality traits factors affecting organisational commitment of employees: A case study of Nike Shoe and Footwear Factories in the Southern of Vietnam*. Master Thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.
- 76) Usha, S. and Rohini, V. (2018). Impact of Quality of Work Life on Work Outcome of Employees in Automobile Companies in Chennai. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 118(20), pp. 787-799.
- 77) Van Breukelen, W., Van der, R. V. and Steensma, H. (2004). Voluntary Employee Turnover: Combining Variables from the 'Traditional' Turnover Literature with the Theory of Planned Behavior. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(7), pp. 893-914.
- 78) Vu, H. V. and Nguyen, T. V. (2018). The correlation among job satisfaction, organisational commitment and turnover intention-A case of technical staff in it infrastructure services sector. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science – Economics and Business Administration*, 13(2), pp. 188-204.
- 79) Yildirim, B. I., Gulmez, M. and Yildirim, F. (2016). The relationship between the five-factor personality traits of workers and their job satisfaction: A study on five star hotels in Alanya. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 39, pp. 284-291.
- 80) Zhai, Q., Willis, M., O'Shea, B., Zhai, Y. and Yang, Y. (2013). Big Five personality traits, job satisfaction and subjective wellbeing in China. *International Journal of Psychology*, 48(6), pp. 1099-1108.
- 81) Zimmerman, R. D. (2008). Understanding the impact of personality traits on individuals' turnover decisions: A meta-analytic path model. *Personnel Psychology*, 61(2), pp. 309-348.